

Research

End-user participation in the conceptualization, planning, design, and development of marketing processes

Dossa Jean-Tychique S Gbeliho¹, Oscar Chijioke Nkwazema², Ibrahim Sangare¹, Jay Ansah Owusu¹, Mariama Janneh³

¹School of Economics and Management, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan, China

²School of Mechanical Engineering and Electronic Information, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan, China

³School of Environmental Science and Engineering, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan, China

Abstract: This paper aims to show the benefit of firms marketing strategy in the integration of customers at various stages of the marketing mix. Studies from the past demonstrate that businesses can profit from incorporating consumers into the creation of new products. But by examining how various elements of a company's marketing plan can raise or lower the likelihood that customers will be involved, this research advances understanding in the area. The advent of digital technology has made it possible for a multitude of businesses to provide their clients with a more individualised level of service and even include them in the marketing process itself. Through many real-world examples, this article demonstrates how consumers may engage in the marketing approach stages; product, price, communication, and distribution of goods and services.

The consumers are the firm's customers, and the areas of customer participation methods that were used in this paper were specific client, modifying client, assembly customer, pricing co-decision maker, customer perception, customer co-creator customers, seller customer, and delivery customer. Following a review of the pros and disadvantages of co-marketing, we stress that the conditions for success must maximise its potential advantages. Some of these requirements include sending customers signals that encourage them to talk to each other, telling the difference between relational skills, making an interactive information system, and listening to what customers say. From these adopted methods, we were able to deduce that the end-user involvement in the firm's marketing strategy helps in customer enhancement, adaptation to needs, product differentiation, deeper customer engagement, valuation of the customer, adaptation to needs, and determination of new uses. Hence, customer involvement increases customer profitability, reduces production costs, and adapts to the client's budget.

Keywords: marketing management, consumer, customer involvement, methods, service, design.

*Corresponding Author: Zhang Qi,

Accepted: 29 June, 2022; **Published:** 08 July, 2022

How to cite this article: Dossa Jean-Tychique S Gbeliho, Oscar Chijioke Nkwazema, Ibrahim Sangare, Jay Ansah Owusu, Mariama Janneh (2022). End-user participation in the conceptualization, planning, design, and development of marketing processes. *North American Academic Research*, 5(6), 177-186. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6812049>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

How much should the corporation include its existing consumers in the process of promoting its products? This has been an important question since the advent of the digital revolution, and it has received an increasing number of inquiries. It has fundamentally altered the relationship between the client and the company. The technological tools required to handle a large number of clients on an individual basis have been made available to businesses as a direct result of this revolution. Some businesses even go one step farther and include their consumers in the marketing process themselves. Nevertheless, in spite of the fact that the necessary technological skills are readily available, a significant number of businesses continue to be reluctant to do so. However, incorporating the customer into the marketing method may be seen as an extension of the traditional marketing technique. Doing so delivers a number of benefits to both the firm and the clients it serves.

When a transactional approach is the predominant one, the core of marketing consists of actions connected to the marketing mix. If you use a relationship strategy, on the other hand, "these activities," also known as the "mix," "are not insignificant," but they must be regarded as support for interactive marketing. Assume that research has been done on the many aspects of relationship marketing, such as management of staff in touch and customer relationship management models. In this scenario, we provide an alternative approach to customer integration by focusing our attention on the components that make up the marketing mix. By doing this, we want to convey that we are interested in incorporating the consumer without causing disruption to the business model. This is an extremely important factor, both from a transactional and a relational marketing point of view. From a transactional point of view, the acquisition of a customised wedding dress results in a sense of fulfillment; nevertheless, this purchase is often not repeated over time (the proposal of custom-made colouring by a hairdresser with whom the customer has a close relationship reinforces loyalty). This article begins by describing the many forms that co-marketing may take before moving on to examine its benefits and how to put it into practice. Next, we will discuss the potential hazards or difficulties that co-marketing may pose. Finally, we emphasize the circumstances necessary for its success.

Research Methodology

Integration of the consumer into the marketing mix: modes of participation			
Stage of the marketing approach	Customer participation	Advantages	Challenges
Product	Specific client	Customer enhancement, adaptation to needs, product differentiation, and deeper customer engagement.	Adaptation of the production tool (costs) and increase in delivery time.
	Modifying client	Valuation of the customer, adaptation to needs, and determination of new uses.	Lack of control over the image of the brand's products.
	Assembly customer	Customer participation and reduction of production costs.	Final result and customer satisfaction within its competence

Price	Pricing co-decision maker	Customization and adaptation to the client's budget.	No budget overruns; compliance with the constraint stated by the client
Communication	Customer creating the message No control over customer perception	Participation, word-of-mouth, animation of the brand community, source of inspiration for professionals.	Creation times, possible recovery by professionals.
	Customer co-creator of meaning	Memorization and complicity.	Complexity of the message, decoding of the advertisement according to the capacities of the consumers.
	Customer delivering the message	Teasing, word-of-mouth and source credibility.	No control over customer perception.
Distribution	Seller customer	Network density, cost, flexibility and vendor credibility.	No control over the image or the affiliate.
	Delivery customer	Increase in coverage and cost.	Problem of controlling transport conditions.

How can a customer become a co-producer in the marketing effort?

It is crucial for businesses to have a solid understanding of how customers may be included in marketing strategies. For the purposes of this paper, the marketing mix analysis grid was used. Imagine for a moment that the customer and the service provider are working together to co-create the service components that are included in the offer (Langeard, 1987). In such instances, the degree of interactivity of the aspects of the marketing mix is dependent on the selections that the managers make, and this option is vital regardless of the strategy that the firm employs (transactional or relational). Table 1 above gives a good summary of the ways to interact with clients that will be talked about in more detail later.

1. The co-producing customer

It is common knowledge that the active engagement of the end user is one of the most important success factors in the service industry. Therefore, in order to offer effective service delivery, the organisation has to have the capacity to convince clients that it is in their best interest to learn and use the talent. Several writers make this recommendation, even going so far as to advocate socialising the client in the corporation in the same manner as an employee (Eiglier, 2006). The growth of the Internet has made it feasible to extend these concerns to the universe of physical mass items, which has resulted in the customer and the corporation being co-producers in this scenario (Wilkstrom, 1995). Consumers in today's market choose items that meet their needs, mould them to their preferences, and give them a distinctive identity.

Depending on where the manufacturing process is in its development, the following are some ways that people can take part in making things.

a. The specified customer

The consumer's function as a specifier is as ancient as the ability to practise "tailor-made" in the world of handicraft (al., 2008). In this situation, the customer provides the options that will be implemented by the product or service provider. In today's market, consumers' unique preferences are influencing product development in previously mass-produced industries (Pepsico, 2010).

b. Assembly-line customer

The client may assume the role of "consumer assembler of components" in this co-production process. With the help of some toy-like pieces provided by the company, he puts the final piece together. A small percentage of the product is produced as a result. There are two possible outcomes depending on the final rendering: conventional or customised (Ramirez, 1994). In the first instance, even though the customer is involved in the production process, he must still follow the rules set by the company to achieve the desired result. To be successful, IKEA must sell low-quality furniture and rely on customers to handle the installation of that furniture. Companies can provide a product in one of two ways without determining the final outcome. Using ready-to-assemble kits, customers can create customised items for scrap-booking, for example, which has grown in popularity as a creative hobby. For marketing to be effective, it must show potential uses for the product and make it easier for the customer to take on the role of a creator (providing assistance tasks and working on the ergonomics of products) (Honebein, 2005) (Cammarano, 2005).

c. The modified customer

Customers can customise the products they buy through a process known as co-production. With Cibie, customers can choose from a wide range of lighting products that can be combined to enhance the look of a vehicle. New products can be inspired by customer requests. In the 1980s, it was fashionable for teenagers to rip their new jeans, and now some car companies allow customers to do the same thing.

2. The co-communicating customer

Messages are exchanged when they are sent from one party to another. When it comes to marketing communications, the media that may be used to connect with customers are carefully selected by marketing communication experts. The latter can only serve as message recipients. Instead of just sending an email or a letter, the goal of communication should be to establish interaction (Vargo & Lusch, 2004). Co-communication means that the customer is part of the process of making the advertising promise, figuring out what it means, and telling other people about it.

a. The customer creates the message

It is common for brands to use pre-tests in communication and advertising as a guide for their upcoming efforts. The advertising message may be crafted by customers in some cases. Customers can become co-creators of their own message through personalised newsletters and promotions. Businesses can use data mining to find out what their customers are interested in and then make their communications more relevant to each person.

b. The customer, co-creator of meaning

A visual metaphor used by Club Med's "The Faces" campaigns encourages viewers to take an active role in decoding a message. Researchers have found a correlation between the user's active participation in each message and the success

of specific advertising processes. In posters and videos, for example, you can see smiling faces in the scenery. As a result, consumers are more likely to associate the brand with the activity (Capelli & Sabadie, 2007).

c. The customer who is delivering the message

With the rise of Web 2.0, the consumer is becoming a medium in and of itself, allowing for the development of messages that are independent of corporate control. Keeping this in mind, it is essential to design a message that can be easily adapted to suit the needs of the audience. To promote the release of the Chevy Volt, GM ran a campaign on TV and the Internet that only showed the numbers "230, 8-11".

3. The customer decides the price.

The consumer is not taken into account when pricing techniques are used. Psychological price or demand price elasticity studies are the only ones that provide an approximate idea of what consumers want in terms of product prices. It's becoming more common to use methods where the customer determines the price. Priceline.com, for example, uses this method of joint pricing to structure its deals.

4. The co-distributor customer

Customer involvement in the distribution process is encouraged because it is often seen as a service. The success of the self-service sales concept has been based on delegating some of the merchant's duties to the customer. Consumers have a say in how their goods are distributed.

a. The customer who is selling

On the Internet, the primary affiliation is as follows: when a customer makes a purchase, they will be redirected to the merchant's website by an affiliate, a business contributor. An example of this trend can be found on the zlio.com website, whereby each individual can become a distributor. Even if you don't have anything to sell, you can set up an online store on this site.

b. The recipient of the delivery

In order to ensure that the company's products reach customers who may not have direct access to the distribution network, consumers can volunteer as delivery people for a company that needs help. Bulk orders can be placed by a group of consumers, and the purchase can be delegated to a member of the group. It's possible to expand the company's reach with the help of these relay customers.

The advantages of co-marketing

Why should a business include its customers in its marketing strategy and tactics? These choices are justified by their legitimacy as well as their added value.

1. Legitimize marketing actions

Marketing is trying to change that by getting its customers more involved. If the customer is involved in making the offer, it will be tailored to what he wants (Capelli & Sabadie, 2005). Any criticism of how the company does business would be like criticising the company itself! So, how can someone criticise the content of an ad message for which they voted?

2. Create value

Adding value is one way that customers are involved in the marketing process. (Vargo and Lusch, 2004) say that for a company to create value today, it needs to include customers in its marketing process. The consumer goes from being a target to becoming a player in the marketing experience. The new logic of marketing says that value is determined by the customer and made together with the customer, instead of being built into the final product.

a. It creates value by reducing costs

Having customers help plan and run marketing campaigns can cut costs for businesses. IKEA furniture is a good example of this. The customer looks for items on the shelves of the warehouse, transports them, and puts them together. The company has many ways to cut costs and pass the savings on to the final price of the product.

b. Create value by improving profits

Consumers are becoming a new source of knowledge for businesses, and they can help make goods and services more useful. Actions taken by a company to communicate can also be seen as less intrusive and, therefore, easier to accept (Friestad & Wright, 1994). The consumer feels less bothered by actions from the outside. When marketers talk to customers, they can get ideas for new products or services for people or uses they hadn't thought of (Co-design according to Cova, 2008).

How do we develop a co-marketing approach centered on the customer relationship?

Integration of consumers into the marketing strategy means that the company can listen to customers, take their requests into account, respond to them in a way that meets their expectations, and get them involved. Customers must be the most important thing to a business, and they must be involved in every part of how it works.

1. Why involve customers?

What should be the primary focus for a business that has the objective of involving customers in the marketing strategy that it employs? The three different types of goals that can be distinguished from one another are: innovation, also known as the search for new ideas; the personalization of the marketing mix in order to achieve a competitive advantage; and the provision of a differentiated customer experience (Ulwick, 2002). Depending on whether they are part of a mostly relational or transactional strategy, these goals can be very specific (like an action that will happen soon) or set for a longer period of time.

2. How much involvement from the customer?

Next, the decision-maker must determine the extent to which the client will be involved in the process. This is critical because the company may incur additional expenses as a result of the co-production. Few companies are able to establish an interactive strategy for their entire marketing mix in a short period of time. Even if the system is fully interactive, a manager must still choose the order in which steps will be done.

3. When to involve customers?

To establish a customer engagement strategy, it's important to know when the customer will be incorporated into this process. Customers have two options when it comes to participating in the offer: either before or after it is delivered. Learning and adaptation are the two stages of product personalization (see diagram 1). It is at this stage that a company learns about the needs of its customers. Either the customer directly reveals his preferences, or the company infers his preferences from his purchase history, website surfing patterns, socio-demographic traits, etc. It is during this stage that the product or service is created or modified to meet the needs of the customer. This can either be done by the customer or by the company itself.

4. How do we engage customers?

The company must take customers' needs into account. Is each customer's participation going to be aggregated or individualized? It is important to know what kind of feedback the customer will receive. An effective participation policy can be developed by answering these questions.

Fig 1. Diagram of Product customization

The risks and challenges of co-marketing

If companies wish to reap the benefits of consumer interaction, they must adapt to this new style of communication. When integrating consumers into the marketing process, it is important to remember that there are both advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, a certain amount of pliability is required to begin a conversation with clients who are becoming more knowledgeable and have more specific requirements. If a company isn't paying attention to its customers, it's not going to be successful. On the other hand, incorporating the voice of the customer into the marketing strategy adds significant implementation delays. Managers are constantly looking for ways to speed up the innovation process, for example, by using customers in a systematic way.

It is also important to consider the client's skills and training while integrating him or her. As a result, a corporation may need to train the consumer in order to ensure that he participates appropriately (Aubert & Ray, 2005). The client's willingness to put in the time and effort required to complete this process is still up in the air. Does participation (or the result's worth) exceed the costs? (Lovelock & Young, 1979).

If you're betting on consumer participation, you'll have a smaller pool of possible customers to choose from, which means you'll have a higher risk of over-segmentation or occupying unprofitable niches. It's possible to think of customer

engagement in a way that goes beyond the typical "sacrifice-benefit" framework. As a result, corporate executives could be persuaded to place greater emphasis on their consumers' engagement in the broader context of social marketing. As long as the events are accurate and credible, they could be a great way to show off the organisation (Capelli & Sabadie, 2005).

The conditions for successful co-marketing

The willingness of business leaders is necessary for the successful implementation of interactive marketing, just as it is for any other business strategy. In fact, it is up to them to create the conditions that will make the customer want to take part, listen to the customer's opinion, and keep this participation going over time.

1. Give customers cues to interact.

An interactive marketing strategy is essential in order to convey the company's intentions to customers. The company will have to let customers know how they can get in touch with them and how they can get involved. Co-communication necessitates that the opportunity to participate in a creative competition of advertising messages be made clear on the packaging of products or at the point of sale. The entire company is involved in this effort, not just the marketing department.

2. Differentiate interpersonal abilities

Internal marketing is a key component of strategies aimed at attracting customers (Gronroos, 1997). Instead of hiring based on a candidate's ability to close sales, companies should look for people with strong interpersonal skills. A retailer that wants to create a memorable shopping experience for its customers must hire employees who have a genuine interest in the products they sell. (Remy and Gentric, 2009) show that a retailer who sets up a consumer experience based on the human connection must recruit employees who are passionate about the product sold in the store rather than good salespeople. The challenge for the company is to enhance the performance of its employees in relational terms, and no longer solely in terms of sales. Indeed, if employees feel that their interpersonal skills are exploited by the company without any recognition, they can damage its image by criticizing it with their network (Cova & Ezan, 2008).

3. Develop an interactive information system.

The foundation of an interactive strategy is a customized information system. By remembering customers' interactions, a company can analyze customer data and adjust to their needs. This is essential. Every time a user connects to the NIKEid site, his or her models are saved in the database.

4. Respect the voice of the customer.

As a final step, it is imperative that the customer be included by showing respect for his suggestions. Unlike other clients, this one does not represent the company in any way. He lacks the necessary skills to perform the duties assigned to him by the company. For example, in Yoplait's publicity contest, the company has to value all competitors, even if they can't deliver a professional performance. For this, she will need to incorporate the winner into the new version of her work so that she doesn't feel like she's being taken away from it. Participative marketing is more likely to keep a customer happy with a company if the customer feels like he or she is valued. In the field of participatory marketing, even more than in the field of relational marketing (Sabadie, 2010), respect for the customer is decisive for the latter to continue to engage positively with the company.

Conclusion

Customers should be involved in every stage of the marketing process for businesses to benefit greatly from it. However, there isn't a single formula that all firms can use to give their clients value. Managers must consider a number of factors, including how involved customers will be. The consumer must also consent to take on this role if the business wishes

to integrate them. The level of knowledge and openness to learning and trying new things that consumers possess determine their competence. Depending on who they are, like in the case of consumer meetings, a consumer may or may not be willing to assist with a marketing campaign (Herbert, 2004).

The question of whether or not customer engagement is reflective of the company's target market thus arises: Are the consumers who choose to participate in these strategies indicative of all customers? It relies on how engaging and interesting the firm is, just like with creating brand communities. It will be crucial to consider how to incorporate clients since they might play a variety of roles in the marketing process. What the management can do will again depend on how the business operates, what its goals are, and what internal resources it has.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Acknowledgement: The author would like to acknowledge and thank his supervisor, Prof Zhang Qi from Economics Department of China University of Geosciences (CUG), Wuhan, China for overseeing the paper and special appreciation to China Scholarship Council (CSC) for granting scholarship to study at China University of Geosciences (CUG), Wuhan, China

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Aubert, B., and Ray, D. (2005), "Training customers to retain them."
- [2] *The Expansion Management Review*, no. 117, June, p. 100–105.
- [3] Aurier, P., Evrard, Y., and Ngoala, G. (2004), "Understanding and measuring value from the consumer's point of view," *Research and Applications in Marketing*, vol. 19, no. 3, p. 2-20.
- [4] Capelli, S., and Sabadie, W. (2005), "The legitimacy of social communication: the role of the advertiser," *Research and Applications in Marketing*, vol. 20, no. 4, p. 53–70.
- [5] Capelli, S., and Sabadie, W. (2007), "Assessing the impact of a metaphorical advertising visual," *Proceedings of the XXII International Congress of the French Marketing Association*, Aix-les-Bains, France.
- [6] Cova, B. (2008), "Consumer Made: When the Consumer Becomes a Producer," *Decisions Marketing*, n° 50, p. 19-28.
- [7] Cova, B., and Ezan, P. (2008), "The Confusion of Consumer and Producer Roles in Brand Communities: a Dangerous Complicity?" *Marketing Decisions*, n° 52, p. 51-60.
- [7] Friestad, M., and Wright, P. (1994), "The persuasion knowledge model: How people cope with persuasion attempts," *Journal of Consumer Research*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 1-31.
- [8] Gourdarzi, K., and Eiglier, P. (2006), "The organizational socialization of the customer in service companies: concept and dimensions," *Research and Applications in Marketing*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 65-90.
- [9] Gronroos, C. (1995), "Relationship marketing: The strategy continuum," *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 23, no. 4, p. 252-254.
- [10] Gronroos, C. (1997), "Value-driven relational marketing: From products to resources and competencies," *Journal of Marketing Management*, vol. 13, no. 5, p. 407-419.

- [11] Herbert, M. (2004), "Consumer meetings: understanding the motivations for participation," *Decisions Marketing*, no. 36, p. 27-38.
- [12] Lovelock, C.H., and Young, R.F. (1979), "Look to customers to increase productivity," *Harvard Business Review*, vol. 57, No. 3, pp. 168–178.
- [13] Merle, A., Chandon, J.L., and Roux, E. (2008), "Understanding the Perceived Value of Mass Customization." A distinction between the value of the product and the value of co-design experience "," *Research and Applications in Marketing*, vol. 23, no. 3, p. 27-50.
- [14] Norman, R., and Ramirez, K. (1994), *From Value Chain to Value Constellation: Designing Interactive Strategy*, John Wiley & Sons.
- [15] PepsiCo (2010), "The Mountain Dew DEWmocracy 2 campaign empowers brand loyalists nationwide to create and launch the next new DEW," www.pepsico.com/PressRelease/The-Mountain-Dew-DEWmocracy-2-Campaign-Empowers-Brand-Loyalists-Nationwide-to-Cr04202010.html (accessed May 17, 2010).
- [16] Prahalad, C.K., and Ramaswamy, V. (2000), "Co-opting customer competence," *Harvard Business Review*, vol. 78, No. 1, pp. 79-87.
- [17] Remy, E., and Gentric, M. (2009), "Thematization of the offer and theatricalization of points of sale," in Rieunier, S. (dir.), 3rd ed., Dunod, ch. 2.
- [18] Sabadie, W. (2010), "Because you are worth it": a study of the status perceived by customers," *Research and Applications in Marketing*, vol. 25, no. 4, p. 7–24.
- [19] Ulwick, A.W. (2002), "Turn customer input into innovation," *Harvard Business Review*, vol. 80, No. 1, pp. 91-97.
- Urban, G.L., and von Hippel, E. (1988), "Lead user analysis for the development of new industrial products," *Management Science*, vol. 34, no. 5, p. 569–582.
- [20] Vargo, S., and Lusch, R.F. (2004), "Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing," *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 68, No. 1, p. 1-17.
- [21] Von Hippel, E. (1986), "Lead users: A source of novel product concepts," *Management Sciences*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 791–805.
- [22] Wilkström, S. (1995), "The consumer as co-producer," *European Journal of Marketing*, vol. 30, no. 4, p. 6-19.
- Zeithaml, V.A. (1988), "Consumer perceptions of price, quality, and value: A means-end model and synthesis of evidence," *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 52, no. 3, p. 2-22.

